

Prototype of biodegradable mulching tool and system and protocol for the implementation

D5.3

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Short Description
<p>This documentation forms the basis for the realization, implementation and management of the project prototype(s) biodegradable in soil mulch film. It includes the prototype objectives, general considerations and recommendations together with the following two sections:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the prototype section that provides a scientific-technological description of the R&I process carried out to realize the prototype (final innovative method / system / tool / product) as result of the testing phase in lab / at small-scale level (WP4) and feedback gathered from the in-field validation (WP5). According to the impact pathway approach, it describes the conducted activities, the reached outputs and outcomes, and the obtained measures of relevant key performance indicators demonstrating the impact; - the protocol section that adopts an operational perspective to describe how to implement and manage the prototype, thus ensuring its full functionality and usability. It includes deployment requirements, procedures, methods, techniques, and practical considerations. Moreover, the protocols generate guidelines (D4.1), practice abstracts (D6.5) and training materials (D5.1).

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1. Background

1.1 Prototype motivations and objectives

Agro-ecological intensification (AEI), which entails application of agro-ecology principles to enhance agricultural productivity is a suitable strategy for smallholder farmers as it promotes utilisation of locally available resources. Compared to conventional farming, AEI has higher potential to sustainably enhance smallholder farmer productivity since it leads to higher production per unit area, lower expenditure on farm inputs, production of diverse foods, increasing ability to get balanced diet, higher ability to produce food all year round, higher ability to produce fodder, stability of production over years, and better maintenance of ecosystem health.

In this field, mulching systems can really help in the intensification of agriculture preserving soil condition while saving inputs, but the end-of-life management of traditional mulch films can be very difficult, they could not be easily recycled and may leave plastic residues in soil if not properly collected. Residues and microplastics generate a relevant impact on the soil health then on crops growth with a progressive yield reduction up to 15%.

Within the FoodLAND project, to boost a sustainable intensification of agriculture through the introduction of combined agro-ecological practices, NVM is developing biodegradable in soil mulch films according to EN17033 standard, so that they can be left in the soil avoiding the production of agricultural plastic waste and relative negative effects for the soil.

NVM designed a range of completely biodegradable and compostable bioplastic materials to provide a low impact environmental solution and solve specific problems in different sectors, such as agriculture including mulch film.

NVM's mulch film are designed in compliance to the OK Biodegradable Soil and the European standard EN17033. The standard defines the specific mechanical and optical characteristics that a mulch films must have to be laid in a fully mechanized way and to efficiently control weeds, but also the chemical features of biomaterial for ensuring a not eco-toxic use in soil. In addition, mulching film complies with the principles on biodegradation and environmental impact of International standards (European standard UNI EN 13432:2002, UNI EN 14995: 2007; American standard ASTM 6400:04).

The main objective of this deliverable is to validate at appropriate scale level a prototype of biodegradable mulching tool and system using the realized comprehensive protocol and practice abstract.

2. Prototype

NVM's mulch film NVM has been optimised for the specific required characteristics: shelf life in the field (duration), colour, mechanisation, thickness and agronomic performance. The tuning of life in field is primarily related to film thickness; it is also possible to make films starting from 10 microns, according to the specific needs of the crop cycle: an average life from 2 to 6 months could be reached using 10 to 15 microns films; 20 microns-thick films can be used for crops with a cycle up to 10 months and beyond 10 months a thickness up to 30-40 microns is suggested.

Table 1: Mulch film applicability and characteristics

Cycle	Duration (months)	Crops	Thickness
SHORT CYCLE	1-3	lettuce	15µm (possible also 12 µm)
MEDIUM CYCLE	4-6	Zucchini, Pumpkin, Solanaceae (tomato, bell pepper, eggplant), Melon, Watermelon, Aromatics (Basil, Parsley,...), Potato, Cabbage, Corn, Industrial tomato, Green bean, Rice, Asparagus, propagating material	15µm
MEDIUM-LONG CYCLE	6-12	Strawberry, Onion, Garlic, Gherkin	from 15 to 18µm
LONG CYCLE	>12	Vine, Small fruit (blueberry, raspberry)	30-40 µm

Biodegradable in soil mulch films can be produced in different colour according to the expected soil conditions and agronomic effect on the crops. Most used mulch film colours are: black (weed control), white / black (double face, soil cooling film), green (soil heating film and PAR cut off).

In the framework of Foodland project, the mulching trials have been carried out in the Tunisian Food Hub under the leading of ISACM and in Tanzanian Food Hub led by SUA. ISACM implemented the mulching trial on tomatoes, a crop on which NVM has collected in the years a significant experience and a lot of agronomical data related to the best agricultural practices to use biodegradable mulch films. On the other hand, SUA implemented the mulching trials on common beans, a crop on which the use biodegradable mulching tool could be considered as experimental. In the table below the main collected characteristics of Tunisian and Tanzanian Food Hubs are summarized and displayed.

Table 2 Main collected characteristics and conditions of Food Hubs

	ISACM – Tunisian food hub	SUA – Tanzanian food hub
Selected crops	Tomato	Beans
Agronomic technique	Open field, conventional practices	Open field, conventional practices
Previous use of mulching	N	N
Mulching laying	Manual	Manual
Irrigation	Drip irrigation	Hoses irrigation
Season test	mid- February and mid-June Temp. min: 9 - 21°C Temp. max: 17 - 30°C	Mid- February Temp. min: 16 - 22°C Temp. max: 28 - 32°C
Test surface	2 mulched rows (25 m) for 2 fields	0,5 acres

The mulching trials, in both Food Hubs, are characterized by similar spring/summer temperature compared to southern Italy. The drip and hose irrigation technology used in Tunisian and Tanzanian Food Hub has been extensively tested and validated in similar condition in Italy. Considering the similar characteristics and conditions of use compared to the NVM expertise in Italy, a fully black biodegradable in soil mulch film was suggested for both regions. For the selected two crops a need of 90 days in soil resistance is required therefore the indicated film thickness was 15 mic.

For the purpose of FOODLAND, FD22_PC01 have been prepared and finalized for mulching trials designed with partners ISACM and SUA. FD22_PC01 was successfully converted in film blowing extrusion in blend with black pigment to obtain a final biodegradable in soil black mulch film.

The formulation FD22_PC01 has been replicated and manufactured into film rolls in 2022, 2023 and 2024 to provide prototypes to be tested in the field in the different test seasons.

Basically the selected mulch film prototype to be validated is: a fully black type, 15 mic thickness, 1000 mm width. In the following table its properties are reported.

Characterizations data are reported in the table here below. The properties have been reported in percentages compared to the properties of a reference biodegradable mulch film with the same formulation, thickness and obtained at the same blow up ratio (BUR).

Table 3 Mechanical characterizations data of black mulch films prepared for the seasons 2022-2024

Sample	Transmittance	Tensile properties				Tear Resistance	
	%	σ_b	ϵ_b	E	En	Direction	Strength
		(Mpa)	(%)	(Mpa)	(KJ/m ²)		(N/mm)
Reference	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	MD	100%
						TD	100%
FD22_PC01	100%	91%	89%	120%	90%	MD	83%
						TD	78%
PC23N1	100%	90%	89%	119%	89%	MD	110%
						TD	95%
PC24N1	100%	105%	95%	95%	102%	MD	105%
						TD	94%

The tensile properties of films resulted to be comparable with the biodegradable black mulch film benchmark. The quality of film is excellent in terms of mechanical properties and of coverage to light (properly Transmittance <3% for ensuring coverage functionality to the light). The films properties and functionality coming from the different two productions are perfectly comparable, demonstrating a good replicability of all processes performed.

The rolls for mulch trials have been prepared on large scale equipment able to reach a film's width of 1000 mm, in 2022, 2023 and 2024.

- For the **first season (2022)** four black mulching rolls (codified as FD_PC01), weight around 15 Kg/each, thickness 15 mic, width 1000 mm have been prepared and delivered to the partners ISACM (Tunisia) e SUA (Tanzania).
- For the **second season (2023)** two black mulching rolls (codified as PC23N1), weight around 10 Kg/each, thickness 15 mic, width 1000 mm have been prepared and delivered to ISACM (Tunisia). Unfortunately, due to a strong delay of rolls delivery, 2023 season of mulching tests at the Tunisian Food Hub was postponed to the subsequent season in 2024. For **the validation season (2024)**, ISACM organized mulching trials exploiting unused film rolls already shipped and well stored in 2023. Therefore, this test could also help to evaluate the shelf life of biodegradable mulch film if the film rolls were to be stored for 1 year under controlled conditions.
- SUA for the validation season, considering the delivery and customs issues, initially guessed the use of the remaining film roll employed in 2022 season. NVM checked the residual tensile properties of remaining mulch film, but a significative loss of mechanical properties has been detected after 2 years since the manufacturing. In such condition the mulch film is weak, and it might not properly ensure the cover of the whole crop cycle or show some damages already during the laying stage. For this a new mulch film roll (10Kg of film, 15 microns, 1000

mm width), based on the biopolymer’s formulation developed, has been prepared and shipped to SUA with the code PC24N1.

Table 4 Prototype supplied

Food Hub	Food Product	Prototype supplied
Enfidha / Chebika (TN)	Fresh vegetables (tomatoes)	30 Kg of roll film (2022) 20 Kg of roll film (2023)
Mvomero / Morogoro (TZ)	Legumes (beans)	30 Kg of roll film (2022) 10 Kg of roll film (2024)
Kamuli (UG)	Cereals, legumes	Agro-ecological intensification practices

2.1 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

The Research & Innovation (R&I) path included several key stages as the materials design, manufacturing, testing and validation.

At beginning NVM collected the key info from ISACM and SUA about Food Hubs conditions and interest crops definition. All these information allowed a customized design of mulch film in relation to the crops selected, season and weather conditions and finally adopted agricultural practices.

Once defined the mulch film type for the use in the selected Food Hubs, a properly biopolymer formulation has been prepared and then converted it into a final biodegradable in soil black mulch film prototype, throughout film blowing extrusion and using a black pigment as biodegradable masterbatch.

The prototype was then characterized by a mechanical point of view and optical properties to check if it offers adequate functionalities and properties mechanical properties to withstand environmental stresses during its lifecycle.

In the selected Food Hubs biodegradable mulching practices were not in use, then a comprehensive protocol of the methods intended to provide guidance to field operators and explain how to implement biodegradable mulch film on the different cropping systems of interest has been drafted. Customized guidelines for each specific Food hub have been provided, to describe a correct use and management of the biodegradable mulch prototype and of its performances monitoring in the field.

2.1.1. First season test (2022) at Tunisia Food Hub

The mulching tests were conducted in two Tunisian food hubs (Enfidha and Chebika) leading by the ISACM Department of Horticulture. The tested crop was open field tomato cultures in both food hubs.

The main objective was to compare the effects of biodegradable mulch films and bare soil on tomato performance in the two food hubs. Ultimately, the objective is to create awareness of the use of biodegradable mulch films in both Food Hubs. Farmers (especially from the neighbouring) were invited at main stages of the experiments to witness and learn from the experiments.

The biodegradable mulching film was designed and provided by NVM, so as to be suitable to the region (climatic and agronomic conditions), the type and mode of selected crops cultivation. A fully black biodegradable in soil mulch film (thickness 15 mic, width 1000mm suitable for manual handling/laying) was selected and designed for both regions of trials. Mulch films were laid manually by farmers and their teams.

Figure 1 Mulch film manually laying at Tunisia Food Hub

A score evaluation method was proposed by NVM, to facilitate data collection on film degradation level. Monitoring was carried out for different observation patterns: film laying, film degradation in the exposed side, film degradation in the underground side, film damages and tear resistance. Collected data was supported by digital photos and weather conditions data for the period of the experiment.

Table 5: Temperatures in Enfidha

Month	Mean day temperature	Mean night temperature
March	17.4	11.5
April	20.6	14
May	24.5	17.4
June	29.1	21.7
July	32.4	24.7
August	32.8	25.6
September	29.5	23.8

Table 6: Temperatures in Chebika

Month	Mean day temperature	Mean night temperature
March	21.8	8.4
April	24.13	14.6
May	32.5	13.6
June	40	23
July	40.2	24.2
August	39.2	25.5
September	36.3	23.7

Mulching films were received by Tunisian partners in February 2022, and then installed at the plots at the beginning of March for both food hubs. The tomato seedlings with 3-4 mature leaves were planted in the open field subsequently on March, 2nd 2022 for Enfidha and on March 5th 2022 for Chebika food hub. The harvest, as last day, occurred on the 24th of June 2022 for both Food Hubs. In Chebika, the mulching film ensured the coverage of 20 juxtaposed lines of 40 meters, which were compared to 20 non mulched lines on the other side of the plot. In Enfidha food hub, however, given that the plots are not disposed similarly, the film roll ensured the coverage of 25 lines of 30 meters, and the mulched lines were alternated with bare ones. Soil characteristics were different among the two food hubs. While it was mainly sandy-silty in Chebika, it was loamy at Enfidha concerned farm. Drip irrigation lines were laid under the mulch. Irrigation was performed just before planting and continued twice per week. Plants were fertigated through drip irrigation at the following rate: 150 kg N/ha, 120 kg P₂O₅/ha, and 200 kg K₂O/ha. Only organic manure was applied before transplanting. The used fertilizers were different among farms, depending on the local supplier with whom the farmers work. The films degradation state was evaluated, at the beginning, 80 and 110 days after transplanting, according to a numerical score system from 1 to 9, where 1 corresponds to highly damaged film while 9 corresponds to no damages.

Many field surveys were carried out to evaluate the film degradation state as well as the overall state of the experiment. Digital field photos were collected at each survey to better show the state of the film degradation. The first visit after the installation of the film and transplanting the seedlings occurred two months and a half later (May 13th for Enfidha and May 20th for Chebika), which corresponds to 80 days after transplanting.

Figure 2 the state of the film degradation at 80 days after transplanting

At this stage, no sign of film degradation was detected at any of the Food Hubs. At 115 days after transplanting, which corresponds to the tomato harvesting, the degradation started to happen, with a score of 7 in Enfidha and 6 at Chebika Food Hub.

Figure 3 the state of the film degradation at 115 days after transplanting

At 185 days after the mulching installation, when the ploughing started to prepare the soil for the next culture, the affected score in both farms was 2 at Enfidha and 1 at Chebika Food Hub.

Figure 4 he state of the film degradation at 185 days after transplanting

Table 7 state of biodegradable mulching film at the survey dates

Days after mulching installation	0	80	115	185
Enfidha	9	9	7	2
Chebika	9	9	6	1

1 corresponds to highly damaged film while 9 corresponds to no damages.

In Chebika farm, the tomato variety was “Dorra”, a highly productive variety, with oblong fruits destined either to fresh market or to processing end. The harvest occurred on many steps (during 3 weeks) depending on the evolution of fruit maturation. The density of plantation was 12000 plants/ha, with an interline of 1.8m, and the distance between plants on a line of 0.5 m. In Enfidha farm, the tomato variety was “Sabra”, a highly productive variety with pear form fruits destined either to fresh market or to industry. The harvest occurred on one step, at the end of the culture cycle (fruit maturity). The density of plantation was 13500 plants/ ha, with an interline of 1.3m, and the distance between plants on a line of 0.3 m.

In Chebika, the field surveys showed that mulched cultures had more intense vegetation, an accelerated starting of the culture, an advanced fruit maturity, a more important fruit calibre, and a higher yield (4 kg / plant) compared to non-mulched cultures (2.5 kg / plant). In Enfidha, the field surveys showed that vegetation wasn’t different between mulched and bare plots. No visual difference was depicted among plots concerning the development of fruits.

Laboratory analysis concerned tomato quality parameters in mulched or bare soils in the two food hubs. They concerned mainly: pH, the acidity, the TSS, the colour, the weight, the calibre, the firmness (figures 1 & 2).

Figure 5 Effects of mulching on tomato quality (a : colour, b : calibre, c : firmness, d :weight) TSP: tomato without mulching; TAP: tomato with mulching; CH: Chebika; N: Enfidha

Concerning the fruit colour, only « a » parameter was significantly different among samples, especially in Chebika Food Hub. No significant effect was detected on calibre, although there was a slight positive effect of mulching on the fruit width, mainly in Chebika Food Hub. Concerning the fruit firmness, it was higher in mulched soil in Chebika, while it was lower in Enfidha Food Hub, when talking about mulching effect. For the tomato weight, biodegradable mulching ameliorated it in both food hubs. Concerning acidity, the effect of mulching was more valuable in Enfidha farm. pH was significantly different between mulched or bare soil cultivated tomatoes, independently of the Food Hub. However, the sense of variation was different depending on the food hub. pH and acidity were inversely correlated (when pH decreases, acidity increases). Soluble sugars level was higher in non-mulched tomatoes, whatever the Food Hub. Only the effect of mulching was significant.

Figure 6 Effects of mulching on tomato quality (a : acidity, b : Soluble sugars, c : pH, d : dry extract content); TSP: tomato without mulching; TAP: tomato with mulching; CH: Chebika; N: Enfidha

In conclusions, biodegradable mulching was more efficient in Chebika than in Enfidha food hub in improving tomato quality, according to the 2 experiments carried out. However, this discrepancy could be explained by different parameters such as the tomato variety, the soil texture, the fertilizers used by the farmers. The experiment in its first trial in only one farm in each food hub should be conducted de novo on more farms for better concluding remarks. Finally considering the results obtained, the fully black biodegradable mulch film based on the biopolymer FD22_PC01 can be considered suitable for the mulching of tomatoes in Tunisian Food Hubs and their related conditions (crop selected, weather).

2.1.2. First season test (2022) at Tanzanian Food Hub

Common beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) is a vital crop worldwide and in Tanzania. Despite their wide cultivation and nutritional importance, common bean yields in Tanzania, have consistently lagged behind their potential. Several factors contribute to this low productivity, including the degradation of soil physical properties and the impact of climate change.

Mulching has been shown to improve soil conditions and enhance crop productivity by preventing water loss, controlling weeds, and modulating soil temperature. This study, aimed at studying and promoting the use of biodegradable mulch in improving the productivity of key crops like beans in different agro-ecological zones of Tanzania. The first stage of study was on-station trials which were conducted in SUA experimental plots in Morogoro. Biodegradable mulching films FD22_PC01 were installed on field beside others different mulching materials (pimento grass mulch and maize straw mulch) to compare the effectiveness and performance of mulching type on the common beans crop. Farmers from the Mvomero Food Hub were invited to witness the experiments and do their own assessment of the performance of different treatments. The experiment was laid out in randomized complete block design (RCBD) in three replications and four treatments: control, biodegradable mulch, pimento grass mulch and maize straw mulch. Holes of 5 cm depth were made by using a sharpened peg of wood nature for plots which had control, pimento grass and straw mulch as treatments. The biodegradable mulch film resulted easily laid by the farmers on the experimental plots (1.7 m x 1.3 m); a sharp razor was used to cut T shaped marks and holes were made using pointed stick with a great care to avoid destruction. Two seeds of Bush 59 bean variety were sown per hole in a spacing of 30 cm x 20 cm and covered with soil. Management practices such as irrigation, pesticide application and fertilization were carried out uniformly.

Figure 7 Beans crop block design

Data collection was carried out from each plot whereby 9 representative samples were taken from middle rows of each plot leaving the guard rows. The data collected were:

- (i) Growth parameters
- (ii) Weed population density
- (iii) yield components

Germination in pimento grass and maize straw mulch was not statistically different. The highest rate of germination was observed at plot with control (98%) followed by plots treated pimento grass (95%) and maize straw mulch (95%) and the least rate was observed plots treated with biodegradable mulch (92%).

Figure 8 % Germination rate

Number of pods per plant was not statistically different in pimento grass and maize straw and control. Plots treated with biodegradable mulch had the highest number of pods per plant (21) followed by control (14) and plots with pimento grass and pimento grass have shown the least number (13) each.

Figure 9 Number of pods per plant

Plots with biodegradable mulch had the highest grain bean yield (11.8 t ha⁻¹) followed by plot with control (6.3 t ha⁻¹), maize straw mulch (5.8 t ha⁻¹) and the least grain bean yield was plot with pimento grass (5.1 t ha⁻¹).

Figure 10 Grain bean yield

The highest plant height was observed at plots treated with control (37.9 cm) followed by plots with biodegradable mulch (36.5cm), with pimento grass (36.0 cm) and the least height was observed at plot with maize straw (34.2 cm).

Figure 11 Height of plant

The highest number of leaves per plant was observed at plots treated with biodegradable mulch (7), followed with those treated with pimento grass (6), maize straw mulch (6) and control (6).

Figure 12 Number of leaves per plant

The highest number of branches per plant was observed at plots treated with biodegradable mulch (4) and those treated with control (4), the least was observed at those treated with pimento grass (3) and those treated with maize straw mulch (3).

Figure 13 Number of branches per plant

The highest number of weeds per plot was observed at plots treated with control (50), followed by those treated with pimento grass (23), maize straw (11) and the least number of weeds was observed at plots treated with biodegradable mulch (4). The highest number of weeds per plot was observed at fifth week (31), followed by week four (25), third week (20) and the least number was observed at second week (11).

Figure 14 Number of weeds per plot

A good functionality of biodegradable mulch film has been observed during the whole crop cycle confirming the mulch use feasibility also for this crop, no previous trials were carried out. By an agronomical point of view, biodegradable mulches performed better than other tested mulches (pimento grass, maize straw) in terms of weeds control, yield, branching, number of leaves, and pods number of beans. Otherwise, biodegradable mulches don't seem improve the seed germination and height of beans plant. From the data collected the use of biodegradable mulch film applied to common beans was demonstrated as an improving for the crop.

2.1.3. Validation final season test (2024) at Tunisia Food Hub

In 2024, a validation trial of biodegradable mulching was launched in the Tunisian Food Hub Chebika, where tomato crop, variety "Dorra", the same as in the season 2022, has been retested. The prototype to be validated is a fully black biodegradable in soil mulch film (thickness 15 mic, width 1000mm suitable for the manual laying) properly designed by NVM so as to be adapted to the region (climatic and agronomic conditions), the type and mode of selected crops cultivation. The mulching film prototype was already provided by NVM in 2023 and stocked by ISACM until the new season of test. For this reason the quality maintenance of the film was verified before laying.

For tomato mulched crop was compared with bare soil tomato, as in the previous test, laying 4 lines of biodegradable mulching film, each of 60 meters. The mulch film was laid

on March 23rd and the tomato harvest took place on June 24th 2024, when fruits were fully mature. Laboratory analyses of fruit quality were done subsequently at ISACM Department of Horticulture.

In Chebika, the soil was mainly sandy-silty. Drip irrigation lines were laid under the mulch. Irrigation was performed just before planting and continued twice per week.

Tomato plants were fertigated through drip irrigation at the following rate, as in the 2022 season: 150 kg N/ha, 120 kg P₂O₅/ ha, and 200 kg K₂O/ha. Only organic manure was applied before transplanting.

Table 8 Temperatures in Chebika (2024)

Month	Mean day temperature (°C)	Mean night temperature (°C)
March	23	14
April	28	16
May	32.5	20
June	37	25
July	41	28
August	39	27
September	36	26

A score evaluation method was proposed by NVM, to facilitate data collection on film degradation level. Monitoring was carried out for different observation patterns: film laying, film degradation in the exposed side, film degradation in the underground side, film damages and tear resistance. Collected data was supported by digital photos and weather conditions data for the period of the experiment (reported below). The films degradation state was evaluated, at the beginning, 80 and 110 days after transplanting, according to a numerical score system from 1 to 9, where 1 corresponds to highly damaged film while 9 corresponds to no damages.

The first visit after the installation of the film and transplanting the seedlings occurred 80 days after transplanting, as for the first trial. At this stage, no sign of film degradation was detected at any of the food hubs. At 110 days after transplanting, which corresponds to the tomato harvesting, the degradation started slightly to happen, with a score of 7. At 185 days after the mulching installation, when the ploughing started to prepare the soil for the next culture, the affected score was 1. Table below reports the state of biodegradable mulching film at the survey dates.

Table 9 Film degradation state at the beginning, 80, 115 and 185 days after mulching installation (Qualitative scale 1 to 9)

Days after mulching installation	0	80	110	185
Chebika	9	9	7	1

1 corresponds to highly damaged film while 9 corresponds to no damages.

In Chebika farm, the tomato variety was “Dorra”, a highly productive variety, with oblong fruits destined either to fresh market or to processing end. The harvest occurred on many steps (during 3 weeks) depending on the evolution of fruit maturation. The density of

plantation was 12000 plants / ha, with an interline of 1.8m, and the distance between plants on a line of 0.5 m.

In 2024, the Chebika field surveys showed that mulched cultures had more intense vegetation, an accelerated starting of the culture. However, the advanced fruit maturity, and higher yield observed in 2022 were not observed in the current season.

Figure 15 Compared vegetation between bare (left) and mulched crops (right) in Chebika food hub

Laboratory analysis concerned tomato quality parameters in mulched or bare soils. They concerned mainly: pH, the acidity, the sugar content (°BRIX), the colour, the weight, the calibre, the firmness (figures 1 & 2). Results analysis showed that no significant effect was detected neither on calibre, nor on firmness or colour of tomatoes. However, the fruit weight was statistically slightly higher ($p < 0.05$) in mulched soil (123.08 g +/- 25.1) than in bare soil (113.68 g +/- 22.78). Fruits acidity and sugar content (°BRIX) were significantly different among treatments ($p < 0.001$), with tomato acidity higher in control than in mulched crop, while sugar content was higher in fruits issued from mulched crop.

Figure 16 Effects of mulching on tomato quality (a: weight, b : acidity, c: Soluble sugars)

In 2022, biodegradable mulching ameliorated the fruit firmness as well as the tomato weight. Concerning acidity, the effect of mulching was not valuable in Chebika farm. However, soluble sugars level was higher in non-mulched tomatoes.

Results showed discrepancies between 2022 and 2024 seasons, in such a way that only the fruit weight was ameliorated in both trials, thanks to the use of biodegradable mulching. Such discrepancies could be due to the fluctuation in the daily weather conditions in 2024, as all the factors were respected in both seasons. However, the farmer (who is the same in both trials) is always convinced with the efficiency of biodegradable mulching use in improving the open field tomato quality and yield and showing his willingness to use it and to encourage the neighbours to do the same. Also for the final season test, the fully black biodegradable mulch film based on the biopolymer FD22_PC01 resulted suitable for the mulching of tomatoes in Tunisian Food Hubs, importantly considering that mulch film wasn't of fresh production, but stocked since the previous year. However, this natural aging, the mulching functionality was not affected, demonstrating a suitable cover during all crop stages.

2.1.4. Validation final season test (2024) at Tanzania Food Hub

The final validation test was on field experiments which were conducted in three distinct agro-ecological zones of Eastern Tanzania.

Figure 17 Field experiment on mulching at Mgeta (in one of the agro-ecological zones), Morogoro in Tanzania

For the field, validation trials, the study was conducted in three villages, which are in three different agro-ecological zones within the major Eastern Plateaux and Mountain Blocks zones of Tanzania (Figure 17).

Figure 18 Agro-ecological zones selected for trials

The villages were Kipera, Ndole, and Mgeta, all in Mvomero district, Morogoro region. Kipera village is in an agro-ecological zone coded E4, which is characterized by rainfall between 800 and 1,000mm per year, altitude ranging from 200 m to 1,000 m above sea level and temperature of 19–31°C. Ndole village is located in an agroecological zone coded E2, characterized by an altitude of 500 to 1,200m rainfall, ranging from 800 to 1,000 mm, temperature 15–30°C. Mgeta is located in agro-ecological zone coded E14, which is characterized by altitude of 500 to 2,000 m. Rainfall between 1,000 and 1,200 mm, temperature 10–25°C. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) to minimize variability and ensure reliable results. Four farmers' fields in a village (site) formed replicated blocks, with each farmer having four plots where three mulch treatments and a control were randomized. Thus, each village (site) had 16 experimental plots. The treatments included Novamont medium-cycle biodegradable mulch. Holes of 2.6 cm² were then manually perforated in each film for seed sowing. Rice husk, sourced locally from Kipera and Dumila villages, was applied in a layer ~2.5 cm thick and spread evenly over the soil surface. Common bean seeds (Uyole 18 variety), commonly grown by farmers in the study area, were sown. One seed was sown per hole with a spacing of 0.4m between rows and 0.1m between plants within a row, following a germination test. Sowing was done on the same day for all plots at each site, including the control plot. Side rows and the plants in the first two holes at the edges of each inner row were excluded from data collection. Plant growth parameters, such as the number of leaves per plant, plant height, number of branches per plant, and ground coverage, were collected at 7-day intervals. A quadrat frame of 1 m² was used to measure ground coverage by bean plants. In each plot, 18 plants were randomly selected and tagged with blue string for growth parameter data collection. Yield components measured from these same bean plants included the number of pods per plant and the number of seeds per pod. Bean plants from the six inner rows were harvested at maturity. Both polythene mulch and biodegradable mulch consistently outperformed the other treatments. Basically, the application of synthetic biodegradable mulch resulted in a substantial increase in biomass production (data in table below).

Table 10 Biomass crop production results

Factors and levels	Plant height (cm)	Number of branches/plant	Number of leaves/plant	Canopy cover (%)
Sites				
Kipera	70.8 ^a	2.6 ^a	5.9 ^a	72.7 ^a
Mgeta	58.7 ^c	1.5 ^b	3.2 ^b	48.6 ^b
Ndole	63.4 ^{bc}	1.5 ^b	3.7 ^b	50.9 ^b
LSD (0.05)	8.1	0.800	0.6	6.335
CV (%)	7.3	24.9	8.5	6.4
p-value	0.029	0.027	<0.001	<0.001
Practices				
PE	68.37 ^a	1.9 ^a	4.6 ^a	61.7 ^a
SBM	68.26 ^a	1.9 ^a	4.4 ^a	60.5 ^a
Rh	62.79 ^b	1.8 ^a	4.2 ^{ab}	57.2 ^b
Control	57.74 ^c	1.8 ^a	3.8 ^b	50.3 ^c
LSD (0.05)	2.6	0.201	0.4	1.580
CV (%)	2	19.2	4.8	5.6
p-value	<0.001	0.288	0.002	<0.001

PE =polythene mulch

SBM = synthetic biodegradable mulch

Rh = rice husk

LSD = least significance difference

CV = coefficient of variation

Letters in superscripts (a, b, c) are used for comparison. Means along the same column and category of comparison bearing different letter(s) differ significantly.

The study also found that mulching significantly influenced yield parameters. There was no significant difference in grain yields between biodegradable mulch and traditional plastic mulch.

Table 11 Crop yields results

Factors	Number of pods/plant	Number of seeds/pod	100 grain weight (g)	Biomass yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
Sites					
Kipera	7.25 ^a	3.63 ^a	37.7 ^a	6.5 ^a	2.48 ^a
Mgeta	6.68 ^a	3.06 ^a	36.7 ^a	6.7 ^a	2.28 ^a
Ndole	6.71 ^a	3.19 ^a	36.6 ^a	7.1 ^a	2.33 ^a
LSD (0.05)	1.76	0.69	1.72	0.51	0.56
CV (%)	14.8	12.2	2.7	4.4	13.7
p-value	0.684	0.196	0.276	0.084	0.675
Practices					
PE	7.50 ^a	3.58 ^a	38.1 ^a	7.5 ^a	2.67 ^a
SBM	7.25 ^{ab}	3.42 ^{ab}	38 ^a	7.2 ^{ab}	2.64 ^a
Rh	6.67 ^{bc}	3.17 ^{ab}	36.5 ^b	6.9 ^b	2.49 ^a
Control	6.08 ^c	3.00 ^b	35.4 ^b	5.4 ^c	1.65 ^b
LSD (0.05)	0.45	0.41	0.8	0.33	0.15
CV (%)	6.1	2.5	1.0	2.5	3.2
p-value	0.001	0.032	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001

PE =polythene mulch; SBM = synthetic biodegradable mulch; Rh = rice husk; LSD = least significance difference; CV = coefficient of variation

Letters in superscripts (a, b, c) are used for comparison. Means along the same column and category of comparison bearing different letter(s) differ significantly statistically

Below, all performance parameters measured at the different trial sites using the different mulching material have been reported in a graphic comparison.

Figure 19 Effects of mulches on soil temperature and soil moisture retention

PE =polythene mulch; SBM = synthetic biodegradable mulch; Rh = rice husk; LSD = least significance difference; CV = coefficient of variation

Figure 20 Effects of mulches on crop growth parameters

Figure 21 Effects of mulches on yield

2.2 Summary of the outputs

2.2.1 Results and achievements

In the first season of testing (2022), the fully black biodegradable in soil mulch film (EN17033) were tried in two Tunisian Food hubs (Enfidha and Chebika) on open-field tomato crops. The biodegradable film, designed and provided by NVM, showed excellent performance throughout the crop cycle, maintaining its integrity until the end of the experiment. Results in Chebika demonstrated significant improvements in crop yield, with mulched plots producing 4 kg of tomatoes per plant compared to 2.5 kg in non-mulched plots. In Enfidha, mulching enhanced tomato weight, though overall differences were less pronounced. Additionally, the mulched soil in Chebika led to faster crop maturity and better fruit quality, notably firmer tomatoes. Film degradation was observed within 180th days, confirming successfully the film's suitability for Mediterranean conditions and selected crop. The validation season confirm just an improving of fruit weight when mulched, also cultures had more intense vegetation and an accelerated starting of the culture. However, improvements on tomatoes quality and specially on yields have been not confirmed as hoped for. These differences may be attributed to the

variable weather conditions observed in 2024, as all other factors were consistent across both seasons.

Beside technical outcomes, an economic analysis based on experimental results from Chebika Food Hub has been conducted by ISACM. The introduction of an agronomic practice such as mulching can really influence the profitability for farmers, specially considering an industrial crop, such as tomatoes. In the table below, a partial budget for the introduction of Biodegradable Mulch in seasonal tomato cultivation has been estimated.

Table 12 Partial budget for the introduction of Biodegradable Mulch in seasonal tomato cultivation

DEBIT (TND/ha)*		CREDIT (TND/ha)*	
1. Additional costs	4310	1.Reduced costs	1247
Rolls of mulch	3500	Irrigation water:	700
Labor cost to install the mulch	60	Fertilizers	187
Labor cost of harvesting	600	Pesticides	360
2.Reduced revenue		2. Additional revenue	7800
Nil	0	Increased yield	6500
		Increase price	960
A. Total additional cost s and reduced revenue = 1+2	4160	B. Total reduced cost sand additional revenue = 1+2	7007
Net change in profit = (B-A)= 7007- 4160 = 2847 TND/ha			

*TND: Tunisian Naational Dinar (1€ = 3.3 TND)

The use of biodegradable mulch in tomato cultivation introduces the initial cost of biodegradable mulch films, generally higher than conventional plastic mulches, but eliminating the need for removal and disposal at the end of the growing season, reducing labor and waste management expenses. In general, the analysis showed that the adoption of biodegradable mulch on the tomato crop is profitable at its current cost. The benefit-cost ratio (B/C) is about 1.7 and the rate of return (ROR) is approximately 70%, primarily due to increased revenue. In addition, also a sensitivity analysis has been carried out, the result indicates that biodegradable mulch use remains profitable even with an 80% cost increased.

Figure 22 Sensitivity analysis of increased biodegradable mulch costs

These simulation results indicate that there is room for increasing water productivity and income through the appropriate use of biodegradable mulch in tomato production. Therefore, these results encourage decision makers to develop strategies for the diffusion of biodegradable in the agricultural sector.

In Tanzania, the same biodegradable mulch was tested on common beans at the SUA farm. The biodegradable mulch outperformed alternative materials like pimento grass and maize straw in weed control, number of pods per plant, and overall yield (11.8 t/ha compared to 6.3 t/ha in control). While seed germination was slightly lower with the mulch, the overall agronomic benefits validated its effectiveness for common bean cultivation in Tanzanian conditions. The mulching application on beans, usually not practiced, actually could be considered as an interesting option of improving for the crop yield. In the validation trials the behaviour and good performances of biodegradable mulch film on beans crop have been well confirmed. Specially the biodegradable mulch film performed on beans crop as the traditional plastic mulch film, both for the soil temperature retention, the soil moisture retention and weed control, but without the issue related to the disposal of traditional plastic mulch. Considering the results obtained, the initial objective related to the saving inputs and the improving of the yield crop could be considered achieved on beans using biodegradable mulching film developed in Foodland project.

Beside technical outcomes, an economic analysis based on experimental results from Tanzanian food Hub has been conducted by SUA and reported in the table below.

Table 13 Partial budget analysis of economic performance of different mulch types

Production cost	Control plot*	Rice husk mulch plot	Plastic mulch plot	SBM mulch plot
1. Variable cost				
Land preparation	1,100,000.00	1,100,000.00	1,100,000.00	1,100,000.00
Sowing	175,000.00	175,000.00	185,000.00	185,000.00
Seed	189,000.00	189,000.00	189,000.00	189,000.00
Weeding	210,000.00	70,000.00		
Mulch		1,886,000.00	1,721,250.00	2,460,750.00
Laying of mulch		375,000.00	205,000.00	205,000.00
Remove of mulch			487,000.00	
Total variable cost (TVC)	1,674,000.00	3,795,000.00	3,887,250.00	4,139,750.00
2. Gross benefit (GB)	1,650.2kg @3,000 = 4,950,600.00	2,492.3 kg @3,000 = 7,476,900.00	2,667 kg @3,000 = 8,001,000.00	2,642. 4 kg @3,000 = 7,927,200.00
3. Marginal return (MR) = GB/TVC	3,276,600.00	3,681,900.00	4,114,050.00	3,787,450.00
4. Benefit–cost ratio (BCR= GB/TVC)	2.96	1.97	2.06	1.91
5. Marginal rate of return (MRR) = GB with mulch – GB without mulch and TVC with mulch – TVC without mulch	1.19	1.38	1.21	

*The exchange rate was Tshs. 2,609.3/= per USD 1 based on Bank of Tanzania (BOT) rates of 26 June 2024.

The Economic analysis conducted indicated that synthetic biodegradable mulch offers promising marginal returns (MR: Tshs. 3,787,450 or USD 1,469) and a benefit-cost ratio (BCR) of 1.91, compared to polythene mulch (MR: Tshs. 4,114,050 or USD 1,595, BCR: 2.06). These findings suggest that synthetic biodegradable mulch is a sustainable and economically viable option for enhancing common bean production across diverse agro-ecological settings in Tanzania. More information can be found in the paper published out of this data (Ramadhani, A. M., Nassary, E. K., Rwehumbiza, F. B., Massawe, B. H., & Nchimbi-Msolla, S. (2024). Impact of mulching treatments on growth, yields, and economics of common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) in Eastern Tanzania. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 8, 1455206. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2024.1455206>

These results in general demonstrate the clear benefits of using certified biodegradable mulch films (EN17033) in agricultural practices. The trials performed indeed demonstrated to Food hub farmers the most potential benefits such as weed suppression, input reductions, moisture retention and tendentially improved crop yields. Besides, the use of biodegradable mulch films presents a sustainable alternative to traditional plastic mulches, overcoming key environmental concerns (soil health, white pollution). Unlike non-biodegradable plastics, which pose disposal challenges and contribute to pollution, biodegradable mulch films break down naturally in the soil, reducing environmental impact and eliminating the need for costly waste management. The trials in fact clearly demonstrated a controlled biodegradation of mulch film after the

harvest of crop. The prototype tested could really boost a sustainable intensification of interest crop in the countries trialled as desired in the project aims.

2.2.2 Relevant production

Relevant production by partners involved in the activities are reported below:

1. Massawe, B.H. Moisan, L., Semu, T., Nchimbi-Msolla, S. (2023). Effects of biodegradable mulch films in common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) performance: On-station trials. *Tanzania Journal of Agricultural Sciences* 22 (2), 161-168
2. Ramadhani, A. M., Nassary, E. K., Rwehumbiza, F. B., Massawe, B. H., & Nchimbi-Msolla, S. (2024). Potentials of synthetic biodegradable mulch for improved livelihoods on smallholder farmers: A Systemic Review. *Frontiers in Agronomy*, 6, 1454060. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fagro.2024.1454060>
3. Ramadhani, A. M., Nassary, E. K., Rwehumbiza, F. B., Massawe, B. H., & Nchimbi-Msolla, S. (2024). Impact of mulching treatments on growth, yields, and economics of common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) in Eastern Tanzania. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 8, 1455206. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2024.1455206>

2.3 Summary of the outcomes

Table 14 Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5)

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Chebika (TN)	Biodegradable mulching	20 farmers
Enfidha (TN)	Biodegradable mulching	20 farmers
Mvomero (TZ)	Biodegradable mulching	24 farmers
Kamuli (UG)	Agro-ecological intensification practices	100 farmers

2.4 Summary of the impacts

Key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Biodegradable mulching was more efficient in Chebika than in Enfidha in improving tomato quality. However, this discrepancy could be explained by different parameters such as the tomato variety ("Sabra" respect to the "Dorra" variety employed in Chebika hub), the soil texture, the fertilizers used by the farmers. In general, the use of mulching practices leads to an increase of income related to improved crop yields or fruit quality (calibre, weight, etc). In first season the mulched tomato resulted with an increased yield

(+60%) than not mulched culture. The quality was slightly improved when the crop is mulched (+10% on weight and caliber). Unfortunately, the final season of 2024 doesn't confirm these improvements on mulched crop, but the different weather conditions may have affected the results.

With regard to Mvomero / Morogoro and Lindi (TZ), from an agronomical point of view, biodegradable mulches performed better than other tested mulches (pimento grass, maize straw) in terms of weeds control, yield, branching, number of leaves, and pods number of beans. For the beans the mulched culture seems to be strongly improved by mulching practices resulted with a doubled yield than not mulched culture. The quality was slight ameliorated when the crop is mulched (+10% on weight and calibre). In this test useful to underline that the biodegradable mulches also performed better than other kind of mulches (pimento grass, maize straw).

Table 15 Key performance indicators

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Chebika (TN)	Biodegradable mulching	At least 20% reduction of input use (herbicides for weed control; water)
Chebika (TN)	Biodegradable mulching	About 30% increase of tomato yield
Mvomero (TZ)	Biodegradable mulching	6% increase in yield compared to rice husk mulching 49% increase in yield compared to no mulch use
Kamuli (UG)	Agro-ecological intensification practices	Increased crop diversity and yield

3. Protocol for the implementation

Deployment begins with assessing soil conditions, climate, and crop types to select the appropriate film thickness and material composition. Procedures include proper soil preparation, ensuring the surface is smooth and debris-free to allow even film application. Methods of deployment, such as mechanical laying or manual placement, depend on the scale of the operation. Techniques like ensuring proper overlap between film edges and using suitable anchoring methods (e.g., soil covering or staples) are crucial to prevent displacement. Practical considerations include monitoring the film's degradation rate, which can vary based on environmental conditions, and ensuring the film's compatibility with irrigation systems. Regular field inspections are necessary to assess film performance and degradation, ensuring it functions optimally throughout the crop cycle.

Implementing and managing biodegradable mulch film requires careful planning to ensure its full functionality and usability. In general, it was found that in African countries plastic mulch film isn't largely used for horticultural crops due to a lack of awareness of its connected benefits. In the framework of Foodland project thus a customized guidelines have been defined for biodegradable mulching to describe the set-up of the experimental fields and management of the biodegradable mulching. Also, quick practical abstracts were collected for operators and farmers to explain products characteristics, storage conditions, and suggestions for a correct use of the biodegradable mulch film in the different cropping systems. NVM collected in the deliverable D4.1 all info on the biodegradable mulching applications as guidance to implement this technological innovation step by step. Below the main procedures and suggestions, from the soil preparation to the crop set-up are summarized.

Preparation of the soil

The methods used for working and preparing the soil (ploughing, milling, etc.) are largely the same as those used with traditional plastics for vegetable crops. However, in order to obtain the best results, both for controlling weeds and for the mechanical performance of the product, it is essential to prepare the soil correctly before laying out the biodegradable mulch film. The soil should be refined and prepared to ensure that stones and any crop residues, particularly harder items (e.g. corn or sorghum stalks, etc.), do not damage the film whilst it is being laid. Special care must be taken when laying mulch film over soil with a high percentage of rock fragments or stones, and if possible the surface must be prepared using a bed former machineries capable of burying the crop residues and rock fragments in the soil.

Figure 23 prepared soil for mulching operations

Laying correctly the film will guarantee its durability in the field. Biodegradable mulch film should not be laid immediately after surface application of manure (even if it is mature), in order to prevent the organic fertiliser from causing early biodegradation owing to its high micro-organism content. However, if fertilisation is conducted one or two months in advance, as usually occurs in normal farming practices, then the film will not be affected in any way.

Laying out the film

The laying out of biodegradable mulch film and the preparation of the soil are the most important operations to guarantee successful results in the field. The film can be laid manually (especially in case of small areas) or mechanically using the same machinery as for traditional plastic film and at similar speed and gear. In the case of mechanically laying it is essential to ensure the correct calibration of the mulch laying machine to ensure the biodegradable film is laid properly: the film tension must be reduced to a minimum to prevent it from being weakened during application, which could make it less effective. It is therefore advisable to adjust the brakes and clutch of the mulch laying machine so as to avoid applying excessive stress to the film during this operation.

Figure 24 Layed mulch film

In the case of manually laying, is simpler to avoid applying excessive stress to the film, but it is advisable don't step on layed mulch film and avoiding mechanical damages (breaks, punctures...) during the hilling the land around the film. It is also advisable to avoid using any rollers which pass over the film once it has been laid out in order to improve its adherence to the soil. Since it is very thin, biodegradable mulch film will stick to the ground perfectly after a few days.

Finally, care should be taken when using rollers for micro-perforations in the field (or to create perforations that allow irrigation waters to penetrate the soil more easily). If not adequately performed, these perforations may allow too much light to penetrate the film, stimulating weed growth which could prematurely damage the film. In order to avoid the problems associated with the improper application of micro-perforations, perforated films are also available. However, if carried out carefully, the micro-perforation of laid film is well tolerated, especially for shorter crop cycles (e.g. spring-summer lettuce).

In particularly windy areas, it is advisable to anchor the mulch film to the ground with small quantities of soil (a shovelful is sufficient) every 2-3 metres on exposed areas. It is advisable to lay the film and transplant cuttings at the same time (normally mulch machine provides laying and transplanting), or to minimise the time between these operations. This will make it possible to take full advantage of biodegradable mulch film.

Crops setup: film perforation, crops transplant, irrigation and agricultural inputs

Perforation is generally carried out when the film is laid and is therefore completely mechanised. It is conducted using the same machines and procedures used for traditional plastics, bearing in mind that biodegradable film is more elastic. Ideally the systems used should perforate the film when it is already positioned on the ground. For manual perforation, equipment should not be used that could produce holes with irregular

edges (e.g. cut tin cans) because these cuts can damage the film prematurely. One of the best ways to make perforations is to use a knife to make a cut in a cross shape or in a T or Y shape. This technique reduces the amount of uncovered land around the transplanted cutting. Holes made using cylindrical implements (including hot cylinders) make it possible to create holes with “clean” edges suitable for biodegradable mulch film.

Figure 25 Mulch film perforation

Controlling weeds and duration of the film

Test results and data from the widespread use of black biodegradable mulch film in the field have shown it is as effective at controlling weeds as traditional materials of the same colour. However, particular attention should be paid to certain species of weeds: field tests have shown that major infestations of horsetail (*Equisetum* sp.) and sedge (*Cyperus* sp.) can damage biodegradable mulch film, which in any case also occurs with thinner varieties of traditional plastic materials. The duration of biodegradable mulch film in the field depends greatly on environmental factors (rain, thermal regimes, solar irradiation, etc.) and therefore it does not depend solely on the action of micro-organisms in the soil. Biodegradable mulch film with a thickness of 15 μm is used to grow a wide range of vegetable species with crop cycles of between 2 and 6 months: from lettuce or leaf crops transplanted in the spring or summer to solanaceae grown in the open field. For crops with a longer crop cycle e.g. the cultivation of strawberries with an annual cycle (or which remain in the field for between 9 and 12 months and which are transplanted in summer/autumn), biodegradable mulch film has shown good performance in typical conditions in Mediterranean areas (Spain and Italy), with thickness of 18- 20 μm . Biodegradable film maintains its mulching capacity for longer in autumnal crop cycles than in the spring or summer, owing to the reduced impact of temperature and solar irradiation, and due to the reduced activity of micro-organism populations in the soil. Finally, for crops for which the soil must be covered for periods of over a year, biodegradable film with a thickness of 40 μm and above is recommended. Applications include small fruits (raspberries) and new vine plantations.

End of the crop cycle

Biodegradable mulch film should not be removed or disposed of at the end of the crop cycle (an obligatory process for traditional plastic film); instead, it is worked into the soil. This operation provides biodegradable mulch film with the ideal environment to end its life cycle through the mineralising action of soil microorganisms, transforming it into water, carbon dioxide and biomass.

Figure 26 stages of mulch film biodegradation

Mulch film made of NVM bioplastics which is left on the surface rather than being worked into the soil will take longer to biodegrade. A range of different operations can be used to work biodegradable mulch film into the soil depending on the type of soil and its state at the time of the operation. Soil conditions and environmental factors are therefore the fundamental elements in determining the biodegradation of the material. For example during the winter, with low soil temperatures, or in lands that remain saturated with water for long periods of time, the biodegradation processes will naturally take longer.

In parallel specific guidelines for field result assessment were also shared with the Food Hub operators to facilitate the mulch film monitoring beside the crops cycle. In this way has been possible to evaluate the suitability of biodegradable mulch film supplied respect to the crop agronomical needs. Properly a score evaluation was defined for the different areas of observation: Laying, film degradation in the exposed side, film degradation in the underground side, damages and tear resistance.

In order to have a properly evaluation during field surveys on the mulch film, a simple numerical score system with values from 1 to 9 was chosen, according to the following observations:

- Damages at laying: 1 = very high number of damages & hard to lay - 9 = no damages & easy laying.
- Film degradation of the exposed side: 1 = 0% uncovered soil - 9 = 100% covered soil.

- Film degradation of the underground side: 1 = film totally disappeared - 9 = film as new.
- Damages (referring only to the exposed part of the sheet): any break, tear, hole, tear that appears on the sheet, reducing its functionality: 1 = very high number of damages - 9 = no damages.
- Tear resistance of film exposed side: 1 = extremely fragile - 9 = very strong, elastic like new one.

Table 16 Assessment plan and monitoring of trials

Description	Survey modality	Timing for check
Degradation exposed side of film	SCORING (1-9)	Every 15 days
Degradation of the underground side of film	SCORING (1-9)	Every 15 days
Damages	SCORING (1-9)	Every 15 days
Tear resistance	SCORING (1-9)	Every 15 days
Laying damages	SCORING (1-9)	At beginning of test
Easy to lay	SCORING (1-9)	During laying
Weather conditions	Climatic station	Season of trials
Photographic survey		Every 15 days
Soil temperature	Temperature probe	daily

3.1 Framework conditions for the prototype

Plastic mulching has helped the intensification of agriculture preserving soil condition while saving inputs, but the end-of-life management of traditional plastic mulch films can lead to different environmental issues. Non-biodegradable plastic residues can remain on the soil if the mulch is not properly removed (white pollution), which increase over the years after its use, and film removal may result in erosion phenomena.

The prototype for biodegradable mulching film is designed to demonstrate the efficiency of biodegradable materials as alternative and innovative solution to the tradition plastics. As the mulching film based on traditional plastic its scope includes usage in open field (small plot by manual laying or medium or big-sized farming plots requiring automatic laying) or in greenhouse. The biodegradable film is designed to protect crops from weeds while maintaining soil moisture and temperature.

Key features include its biodegradability, easy installation, and its applicability on different crops. Thanks to its biodegradability final users interacts only at initial setup of mulching by laying the biodegradable film on the soil, after the harvest biodegradable mulch film should not be removed or disposed, but it is worked into the soil.

Most limitations of prototype respect to mulching based on traditional plastic include its reduced effectiveness and field shelf life in extreme climates (e.g., heavy rains or drought) or due by strong soil activity (e.g. use of manure as fertilizer could lead to early biodegradation owing to its high micro-organism content).

3.2 Prerequisites for the prototype / Technical architecture

The technical components and infrastructure required to build the mulch film prototype basically include the equipment for performing a blown film extrusion. This process involves melting a polymer resin in an extruder, then molten polymer is then forced through a circular die to form a thin, continuous tube. Air is blown into the center of the tube, inflating it like a balloon, which stretches and cools the film as it rises. The inflated bubble is then collapsed into flat sheets using guide rollers. The film is then wound onto rolls. For agricultural mulching applications it is important to reach the suitable width of film (> 1000 mm), this aspect is correlate to sizing of the blown film station.

The primary inputs consist of raw materials like biodegradable biomaterials and additives. In particular colour masterbatches, based on biodegradable polymer matrix, are required to prepare the full black biodegradable film prototype validated in Food Hubs during the project. Personnel involved should have expertise in polymer processing, material science, and agricultural applications to ensure proper formulation and manufacturing. Key costs include the procurement of raw materials, equipment setup, labour, and energy consumption during production.

Table 17 Requirement description

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Blown film station	M
2	Biodegradable biopolymers and color masterbatch	M
3	<i>Personnel skilled in polymer processing</i>	1
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

3.3 Implementation plan

The implementation process for adopting biodegradable mulch film in African Food Hubs after the project could involve several key stages, with an estimated timeline of 12 to 18 months.

During the project logistic issues has been observed sometimes critical for the tests carrying out: important delays related to customs clearance and transport of mulching prototypes to Food Hub occurred, demonstrating the need to establish a local supply-chain for the potential future mulch film production.

According to this need, the implementation process should be initially focused on the establishment of partnerships with suppliers of biodegradable materials (0-3 months). During this stage logistics for importing the raw material, including customs clearance and transport to local converters, should be well defined.

The second phase (3-6 months) involves the scouting of suitable local film producer, eventually providing for adapting existing production facilities. Properly speedy way could be to detect shopping bag manufacturers which in some cases already able to

handle biodegradable polymers. In this case with small equipment adjustments and staff training such manufacturers could easily manage even the mulch film production, sharing same technology.

At moment, NVM is in contact with several African manufacturers, located in Tunisia, Mozambique, Ivory Coast and South Africa, who successful converted proprietary biodegradable biopolymers into common film applications (shopping bag).

The pilot production phase (6-9 months) will focus on small-scale manufacturing to ensure manufacturing reproducibility, quality control, and material performance in local conditions. Key milestones include the successful import of biodegradable materials, completion of equipment modifications, and the production of the first batch of mulch films. The final phase (9-18 months) will see full-scale production, marketing, and distribution to local farmers, alongside ongoing monitoring of material performances in several agricultural environments.

3.4 Management

The management and maintenance of biodegradable mulch film can differ significantly from non-biodegradable plastic mulching film specially for the different shelf life of materials. During the use in field the aging effect on biodegradable mulch more affects the film functionality than traditional plastic film. For this a regular monitoring of the film's integrity, checking for early signs of wear, tearing, or premature degradation is needed during the crop cycle and related eventually to the agricultural practices followed. Control measures can include eventually also the adjusting irrigation or farming practices to prevent unintended damage on biodegradable mulch film installed. Also an early degradation due to extreme weather conditions, which can reduce its effectiveness, can occur. Carrying out the suggested periodic assessments helps ensuring it aligns with crop needs and environmental conditions.

Post-season no management action is needed for biodegradable mulch film, it's useful to monitor a film's complete biodegradation and ensure minimal residue remains in the soil. The biodegradable mulch eliminates the need for disposal and reduces long-term environmental impact, offering a more sustainable solution. In contrast, non-biodegradable plastic requires ongoing control to prevent tearing, shifting, or water pooling, as well as logistical planning for its disposal, which often incurs additional costs and contributes to landfill waste.

Finally the processes used for storing biodegradable mulch film are different from those used for the storage of traditional plastics film. When not being used, rolls of biodegradable mulch film must always be stored inside the farm store in their original packaging, protected from water, light and sources of direct heat. If the rolls is not replaced in its original packaging after use, it is advisable to keep it upright to avoid flattening, deformation or breakage. Various tests have shown that when biodegradable mulch film is properly stored it can be used in subsequent seasons, with satisfactory performance and agronomic behaviour. Also the final season trials carried out by ISACM in 2024, using a roll film produced in 2023, demonstrated the suggested shelf life of unused biodegradable mulch film.

Accidental breakages caused by improper storage of materials or damage during transport may have a negative impact on the life of the film in the field. If possible, any damaged parts of the film should be removed before use.

4. Conclusions

The fully black biodegradable in soil mulch film (EN17033) based on the developed biopolymer FD22_PC01 was positively validated for the mulching practices on tomato at Tunisian Food Hubs and on the beans mulching at Tanzanian Food Hubs. In particular, the mulching application on beans, usually not practiced, resulted surprisingly a ready practice for the intensification of the crop.

Results achieved in FoodLAND Food Hubs suggests that the biodegradable mulch films could be an efficient alternative to traditional plastic films, minimizing environmental impact and saving time and resources in managing the end-of-life of mulched crops also for African countries.

The biodegradable mulch film adoption in the African agronomical practices was demonstrated as feasible, however it requires an important effort for creating awareness in local farmers and ready availability of the validated mulch tool. The creation of biodegradable materials supply chain and infrastructures for a local production of mulch films are critical for the implementation plan of the validated tool. Local film producer, already able to handle biodegradable polymers, could be considered good candidates for adapting existing filming facilities and ensuring a production of biodegradable mulch film for the African area.

